

Electrical conductivity of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in ethanol at 25 °C

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Abstract : The conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate has been measured in ethanol at 25 °C. The data were analyzed using the Fuoss-Onsager equation for 1 : 1 associated electrolytes and the characteristic functions, Λ_0 (conductance at infinite dilution), a^0 (contact distance) and K_A (association constant) were computed. K_A values were analyzed on the basis of the solvent separated - ion pair model. The electrostatic Stoke's radii $R^+ + R^-$ were calculated and their sum was compared with the value of a^0 confirming the above model.

Keywords : Conductivity, acetylthiocholine, ethanol, ionic association.

Introduction

In continuation of our conductometric studies on acetylcholine and *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in simple solvents¹, the present work aims at determining the conductance values of the solution of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in pure ethanol at 25 °C to throw light on the behaviour of these salts in simple solvents and to examine the validity of Fuoss-Onsager equation for 1 : 1 electrolyte².

The association constant and the closest distance of approach (a^0) for the studied salts have been evaluated. These values have been used to discuss qualitatively the nature of the ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions of the *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in pure ethanol.

Results and discussion

The measured equivalent conductance are shown in Table 1. An approximate value of Λ_0 (estimated from the extrapolation of Λ vs $c^{1/2}$ plot) introduced to Fuoss-Kraus-Shedlovsky (F.K.S.) equation, to obtain accurate values,

$$1/\Lambda S_{(z)} = 1/\Lambda_0 + (C\Lambda S_{(z)}^2)/(K_D\Lambda_0^2) \quad (1)$$

where K_D is the dissociation constant and $S_{(z)}$ is the Shedlovsky's function which was tabulated by Daggett for different values of z . The value of z could be calculated from the following equation,

$$z = \alpha (CA)^2/\Lambda_0^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

Table 1. Conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in ethanol at 25 °C

<i>s</i> -Acetylthiocholine bromide		<i>s</i> -Acetylthiocholine iodide		<i>s</i> -Acetylthiocholine perchlorate	
$10^4 C^a$	Λ^b	$10^4 C$	Λ	$10^4 C$	Λ
				10.8971	40.58
15.7622	34.06	9.09495	37.68	6.62917	43.26
8.71144	36.48	7.09128	38.75	5.47126	44.14
7.09806	37.21	5.84398	39.50	4.74321	44.76
6.08999	37.69	4.84497	40.17	4.05488	45.44
5.04438	38.26	4.15362	40.64	3.46630	46.01
4.38676	38.67	3.64392	41.04	3.08213	46.43
3.99242	38.90	3.27557	41.36	2.71963	46.87

^aequiv⁻¹, ^b Ω^{-1} equiv⁻¹ cm².

In the equation α is the limiting tangent. The plot of $1/\Lambda S_{(z)}$ vs $(C\Lambda S_{(z)}^2)$ gives $1/\Lambda_0$ as the intercept and $1/(K_D \Lambda_0^2)$ as the slope. More accurate values of Λ_0 , a^0 and K_A are obtained from Fuoss-Onsager equation² with the aid of a special computer program (IBM-PC) starting with the value of Λ_0 which was obtained previously from (F.K.S.) equation. The accuracies required in these computations are

± 0.02 for Λ_0 , ± 2 for $J < 200$, ± 5 for $J = (200 \rightarrow 1000)$ and ± 10 for $J > 1000$.

Fig. 1 shows the variation of a^0 with J . By the aid of

Note

Fig. 1. Variation of J with a° in ethanol at 25 °C.

this calibration curve, the average value of a° is determined from the corresponding average value of J (which is previously obtained from the computer readings), knowing that J is a function of a° and is represented by the following equation³,

$$J = \sigma_1 \Lambda_0 + \sigma_2 \quad (3)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 are the functions of J . The derived constants are represented in Table 2. Λ_0 increases from *s*-acetylthiocholine bromide to perchlorate according to the ionic equivalent conductance of anions. The values of a° decrease with increasing the size of anions indicating that it controls the extent of ion pairing. The solvation of these anions increases in the order: $\text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which is in accordance with the trend of a° values. From

the electrostatic point of view, since the distance between the cation and the anion increases in the same order, the forces of attraction increase in the order: $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^-$.

In an earlier study¹ on the conductance of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate in *n*-propanol at 25 °C authors found that the order of solvation (a°) is, $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$ while K_A is irregularly varied with the size of anion. The gradual decrease of a° with the K_A among the studied salts was attributed to the relative position of the anion with respect to the cation which may not be completely spherical. In a second study¹ on the conductance of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in 2-propanol at 25 °C the order of solvation (a°) is, $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$, which is same as the present one.

Conductance measurement of acetylcholine halides and perchlorate in *n*-butanol at 25 °C gives the order of solvation (a°) as $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{ClO}_4^-$ and the trend of K_A regularly increases with the increase of the size anion (except iodide)¹. Conductance of quaternary ammonium salts of Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and ClO_4^- in *n*-butanol at 25 °C gives the order of association as $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$ which is also similar to present work⁴.

Table 2. The characteristic parameters for *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in ethanol at 25 °C derived from Fuoss-Onsager equation

Salts	Λ_0^a	J	$a^\circ (\text{A}^\circ)$	K_A	σ_A
S-Ac-Br	43.42 ± 0.6303	2053.1	6.5089	142.42	0.00394
S-Ac-I	46.00 ± 0.4462	2060.2	6.0046	188.22	0.01550
S-Ac-ClO ₄	51.96 ± 0.4216	2197.2	5.5363	250.54	0.01881

^a $\Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$.

The increase of K_A with increasing the size of anion of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate can be explained in the light of the U term included in the following equation⁵,

$$\ln K_A = \ln (4\pi N a^3/3000) + (e^2/a^0 DKT) + U \quad (4)$$

where, $U = \Delta S/K - E_s/KT$

$\Delta S/K$ is the entropy Boltzman constant ratio which illustrates the probability of the orientation of solvent molecules around the free ions, and E_s/KT is an energy relationship which includes the energy of solvent molecules with respect to both free ion and ion pair. The values of U term of *s*-acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate are given in Table 3. The results reveal that the value of U slightly increases from Br^- to ClO_4^- . The entropy term becomes more predominant than the ion-

Table 3. Calculated values of K_2 and U for *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in ethanol at 25 °C

Salts	K_A	K_1	K_2	U
S-Ac-Br	142.42	24.003	4.933424	1.780601
S-Ac-I	188.22	25.3709	6.418737	2.004009
S-Ac-ClO ₄	250.54	27.51261	8.106369	2.208974

dipole term. Therefore the solvent separated ion-pair model can be now applied⁶. In this model a multiple step association is suggested, and can be illustrated by the following scheme :

Table 4. Calculation of radii of ions for *s*-acetylthiocholine salts in ethanol at 25 °C

Salts	Λ_0^a	λ_0^{-a}	λ_0^{+a}	Av. λ^{+a}	$\lambda_0^- \eta_0^b$	$\lambda_0^+ \eta_0^b$	R^{-c}	R^{+c}	$(R^- + R^+)^c$	a^{0c}
S-Ac-Br	43.42 ± 0.6303	24.23	19.19		0.26697		3.069303		6.86752	6.5089
S-Ac-I	46.00 ± 0.4462	26.75	19.25	19.58 ± 0.57	0.29473	0.21573	2.78016	3.79822	6.57838	6.0046
S-Ac-ClO ₄	51.96 ± 0.4216	31.65	20.31		0.34872		2.34974		6.14796	5.5363

$a^0 \Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$, $b^0 \Omega^{-1} \text{equiv}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{p}$, $c^0 \text{Å}^0$.

The association constant is given by the following expression :

$$K_A = K\Sigma = (C_{(\text{ion-pairs})}) / [(C_{(s\text{-acetylcholine})^+}) (C_{x^- (\text{solvent})_n})] = K_1(1 + K_2) \quad (5)$$

where, $K_A = K\Sigma$ is obtained from the conductance measurements,

$$K_1 = 4\pi N a^3/3000 e^b \quad (6)$$

K_2 was thus calculated. The results compiled in Table 3, indicate that K_1 increases from Br^- to ClO_4^- i.e. the ion-pair prefers the more solvated form (case I) than the desolvated form (case II).

The electrostatic radius (R^+ or R^-) is given by Stoke's equation,

$$R^{(+ \text{ or } -)} = 0.8194 \times 10^{-8} / \lambda_0^{(+ \text{ or } -)} \eta_0 \quad (7)$$

where λ_0^- is obtained from the intercept of the straight line resulting from the plots of Walden products $\Lambda_0 \eta_0$ vs the reciprocal of the molecular weight as previously discussed⁷, while the λ_0^+ for *s*-acetylthiocholine⁺ is represented by the average value of λ_0^+ of the bromide, iodide, and perchlorate salts. Form the data in Table 4, it can be seen that the value of a^0 is smaller than the electrostatic radii ($R^+ + R^-$). The surprisingly lower a^0 values are probably attributed to ion association.

Experimental

s-Acetylthiocholine halides and perchlorate were purified as reported elsewhere⁸. Ethanol (BDH) was purified using the following method. Ethanol was left in contact with molecular sieves 4A for about 24 h with frequent shaking. It was then distilled, refluxed with silver nitrate for 24 h and distilled again.

The second distillate was refluxed again with analAR magnesium turning for 24 h and then distilled again. The

third distillate was kept in contact with activated alumina for 24 h with occasional shaking and then distilled in a fractionating column about 1 m long and only the middle portion with constant boiling point was collected.

The specific conductance for purified ethanol was found to be $(1.21-1.36 \times 10^{-8}) \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The conductivity water was obtained by passing ordinary distilled water from a tin still over a 50 cm long Elgastat deionizer, and guarded against contamination with atmospheric CO_2 by soda lime. Its specific conductance was $(2-4 \times 10^{-6}) \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. The density (d) of pure ethanol was determined using a 25 ml Pycnometer at 25 ± 0.02 °C and was found to be 0.78744 g/cm^3 . Its viscosity η was measured at 25 °C using viscometer with a flow time of 250 s. It was found to be 1.1018 cp. The dielectric constant value was used as reported in the literature⁶. All solutions were prepared by reducing weight to vacuo. Salts were weighed on microbalance which read to ± 0.1 mg.

Dilution was carried out successively into the cell by siphoning the solvent by means of dispenser. An Erlenmeyer cell with bright platinum electrodes was used. The cell constant was calculated ($0.05443 \pm 0.43\% \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

using the Lind-Zwolenik-Fuoss equation⁹.

A "Pye" 11700 conductance bridge was used for measuring the resistance of solutions at 5 Kc/s.

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